

A Proposed Conception To Activate The Role Of Saudi Universities Through Their Programs In Encouraging Free And Critical Reading Among University Youth, In Both Arabic And Foreign Languages

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 24, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 28, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Critical reading, Saudi Arabia, Universities, Role, Students, Develop</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5610076</p>	<p><i>The critical understanding of text written in the most widely spoken foreign language (English) has become a bedrock to many academic and social breakthrough as majority of the world's research documents are written in English while an understanding of Arabic text gives context to the written text and as such the significance and importance of critical reading in tertiary institution is on the increase; as employer are seeking for graduate that are capable of intense reasoning that necessitate development of ideas, unraveling of hidden concept and also having a general problem solving skills which is vital for any meaningful development and inventions. The research aims to seek the role of Saudi Universities in developing free and critical reading among University Students in both Arabic and English Language as the development of any nation depends on competent and skilled graduates that are capable of critical thinking geared towards problem solving and the application of knowledge. A simple random sampling technique was utilized for this study. 100 questionnaires were administered to the individuals, who were randomly selected by the researcher. The researcher utilized all the questionnaires as they were all appropriately completed and returned. It was revealed that training students to practice reading in the university, and informing them of their rights and societal duties through comprehensive reading about them would enhance their critical reading skill. Finally, holding specialized training courses and workshops for faculty members to provide students with the knowledge and skills necessary to develop their abilities; to teach students reading subject matter to students, each according to his specialization is necessary in developing critical reading skill among them, not only in Arabic but also in the English language.</i></p>

Introduction

Foreign language is a language used as a means of communication in addition to one's mother tongue. It is often times referred to as a second language. The English language is the most spoken foreign language with millions of speakers worldwide while Arabic is the Semitic language of the Arabs, which is spoken throughout the Middle-East and North Africa. The critical understanding of text written in English has become bedrock to many academic and social breakthroughs as majority of the world's research documents are written in English while an understanding of Arabic gives context to the written text. Therefore, the development of any given nation is tied to the development of competent and skilled graduate that are capable of critical thinking necessary for the contribution of their quota towards their nation's goal in all sphere of life and as such the importance of reading cannot be over emphasized as it forms the foundation to any meaningful learning process. Palani (2012) is of the opinion that, "effective reading is important avenue of effective learning and reading is interrelated with the total educational process and hence, educational success requires successful reading habit". It is said that "leaders are readers" which further states the importance of reading and most especially Critical reading for the preparation of student for future career endeavors and significant contribution to the Nation at large and as such this research is geared towards the role of Saudi Universities in developing free and critical reading among University Students in both Arabic and English Language.

The Concept of Critical and free reading is necessary to spurn critical thinking which is a vital tool for problem solving as it relates to the "truths and faults of the text, and interpreting its content". Literacy Gains (2009) "defined Critical Reading as an attitude, an emotional and intellectual behavior, a mental stance that the reader reveals while reading a text". Critical Reading "is the science and art of examining and evaluating a text and adopting a perspective, according to Paul and Elder" (2008). The definition of Critical reading is a revelation that it is an advance form of reading which is aimed at reading in between lines and understanding the concept and ideal of the given text which signifies that this form of reading differs from leisure reading.

The significance and importance of Critical reading in both English and Arabic in tertiary institution is on the increase as employer are seeking for graduate that are capable of intense reasoning that necessitate development of ideas, unraveling of hidden concept and also having a general problem solving skills which is vital for any meaningful development and inventions. White (2004) noted the purpose of Critical reading as:

“The purpose of critical reading is to develop independent thinking and skills in analysis and judgment. The student must first recognize what the author is attempting to say. Secondly, they must weigh the evidence for reliability, accuracy, and representativeness. They must be able to separate opinions from facts, and identify the viewpoints and biases of the writer. In analyzing the material, the reader checks the author's assumptions and logic and traces the relationship between the evidence, assumptions, and conclusions” (White 2004, p.42).

It is therefore important for students to develop a good reading habit that is vital for the processing and analyzing of a given text which helps in extraction of information which in turn aids providing answers to problems on a regular base.

Ndethiu (2017) noted that “When students join the university for the first time as undergraduates, they do not bring these critical abilities to their new learning environment. Yet, without good reading habits, it is impossible to engage effectively in the complex intellectual processes that define the higher educational experience. Good reading habits make it possible for students to experience *higher* learning in the authentic sense of that term. Without good reading habits access to information is limited and a critical response to academic material is largely obscured” which further states the importance of Critical reading and the role higher institution in developing a good and critical reading culture among students.

Programs that aid the development of critical reading should be given utmost attention as it guarantees the development of successful graduate from universities which necessitate this research which is aim at seeking the role of university in encouraging critical reading among their Students in both English and Arabic. The research is geared towards answering the under listed questions:

- What are the goals of universities in promoting free reading among students?
- What is the role of universities in achieving that skill that is consistent with the Kingdom's vision and objectives?
- How universities are directed to set special goals in their plans and programs for this important skill to spread culture among students in universities?
- What are the appropriate mechanisms to activate the role of universities in developing free and critical reading because of their role in the theory of knowledge?
- How does a university professor develop the faculty of free reading and use it to develop scientific research?
- What are the obstacles to activating free reading among professors and students in universities?
- What are the proposed solutions to achieve this practice because it is one of the successful practices and is consistent with the scientific explosion of knowledge, and the transfer of students and professors from the limited sea to the extended ocean?

2.0 Literature Review

Critical reading is defined by Özdemir (2002, p.19); individuals think about what they read, evaluate what they read and it become habit to use their own value judgments while they are reading. Carvetti, Pardales and Domico explained the critical reading is an evaluate process the text while reading in the way of trueness and validity. Reader who don't read critical generally accept the ideas in text incontestable and memorize, reader who read critical watch out the text what it tell about, which idea support them and how the ideas describe. (Aşılıoğlu, 2008: 7).

Ahmed et al (2012) carried out a research on the problem faced by student in reading in Arabic. They author noted that a high percentage of students prefer to read Arabic text as a leisure activity and also Arabic text that relates to religion and such this student do not have critical understanding of Arabic text due to their reading habit of skimming through Arabic text. They suggested a critical approach of reading to remedy the challenge of students not reading Arabic text.

(Mclaughlin & DeVoogd (2004) noted that “reading critically differs from other forms of reading in that the reading act goes beyond the literal meaning by questioning the functions and purposes of the text”. Turner (1988) describes it as “...reading with awareness of similarities and differences between what the reader has already seen and what he is seeing in the text he is reading” (p.186). It is clear that the process involves analytic thinking and evaluating what one reads (Mclaughlin & DeVoogd, 2004) and also requiring higher reasoning skills, comprehension skills such as making inferences, reasoning and judging.

Aricı (2008) indicated that it is the ability to enter a communicative interaction with the text and to make interpretations and evaluations regarding it. Altunsöz (2016) defined critical reading as reading by asking

questions regarding the conflicts, consistencies, and inconsistencies in the thoughts or expressions in the text and the reasons why it was written.

Krug (2010) found that there is a direct relationship between teachers' experiences and applications that students learn to question texts using critical literacy approaches, criticize social injustice, engage in social acts, and finally that every student can learn how to read critically.

(Aşlıoğlu, 2008) carried out an on the relationship between Critical Reading and cognitive learning. He found out that University Student learning is mostly restricted to vainmemorizing and remembering for the purpose of examination and as such they do not possess critical reading skills. He concluded that surface reading cannot achieve higher intellectual properties such as Application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation.

Koray and Çetinkılıç(2020) noted that “the most important condition for improving Critical reading, and thus critical thinking, are educational programs that are specialized for different disciplines and subject areas or have multidisciplinary applications”. Examining the effectiveness of such programs, which are expected to have common points in terms of high-level thinking skills, is only possible with scientific studies. They author added that student should engage in International exams such as PISA, TIMMS, and Progress in International Reading Literacy (PIRL) which will aid in ascertaining students' reading retention and comprehension, their ability to transfer lessons learned to daily life, and problem-solving skills. More so, reading habit must be introduced to students to develop their analytic, synthetic, and evaluation skill in preparation for these international exams. They concluded that open ended question should be implored in assessing of student rather than closed ended question.

Ndethiu (2017) believes that universities have not adequately prepared students for the real world as it pertains to effective reading. The author noted that “In the real world, the ability to read and understand, to locate information for themselves and for others, quickly and efficiently is demands that have intensified with the increase in information and information technologies”.

Research Methodology

Study Method

The mainpurpose of this study was to explore the role the role of Saudi Universities in developing free and critical thinking among university students. A simple random sampling technique was utilized for this study. The survey design included questions in relation to socio-demographic characteristics; the role of university teaching objectives in promoting free and critical reading among young people in its academic and training educational programs (first axis); The most important procedures, means and teaching mechanisms that must be implemented by those responsible for plans and programs in developing the skill of young people to read (second axis) and; obstacles to activating the role of the professor in training young people to read in universities in a way that develops scientific research and serves the country's research priorities (third axis).

Sample Size:Our study population was female individuals affiliated with universities in Saudi Arabia, whether they are students or employed. 100 questionnaires wereadministered to the individuals, who were randomly selected by the researcher.The researcher utilized all the questionnaires as they were allappropriatelycompleted and returned.39 percent of the 100 participants were government employees and 27 percent were full-time students. 21 percent of the respondents said they do not work, while the remaining 9 percent were people retired from their profession. The sample showed representation from most working classes in Saudi society.

Data Analysis:The data collected was statisticallyanalyzed. Descriptive statistics of percentage and pie charts were used in the presentation of the collected data.

Result and Discussion

The following result will determine (a) the goals of universities in promoting free reading among students (b) the role of universities in achieving that skill that is consistent with the vision and objectives of Saudi Arabia (c) how universities are directed to set special goals in their plans and programs for this important skill to spread culture among students in universities (d) the appropriate mechanisms to activate the role of universities in developing free and critical reading because of their role in the theory of knowledge (d) how free and critical reading can be develop and applied in scientific research (e) the obstacles to activating free and critical reading among professors and students in universities (f) ways to achieve free and critical reading.

4.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics

The socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents of this study have been represented in percentages and charts. The sample asked 100 randomly selected members to fill in the questionnaire. The Sample showed that most (88%) of the participants at least held a university degree, while 22 percent of participants held a Master's or higher degree (see *Figure 1*).

Figure 1: Educational Qualification of the Respondents

39 percent of the 100 respondents were government employees and 27 percent were full-time students. 21 percent of the sample said they do not work, while 9 percent were people retired from all and every profession. This is represented in *figure 2* below. The sample showed representation from most working classes in Saudi society.

Figure 2: Profession of the Respondents

Also recorded in the study were the social status, gender and age of the respondents. These were all represented at the **Appendix I** section [Figure (a), Figure (b) and Figure (a)] of this study.

The research is done on three axes: the role of university teaching objectives in promoting free and critical reading among young people in its academic and training educational programs (first axis); The most important procedures, means and teaching mechanisms that must be implemented by those responsible for plans and programs in developing the skill of young people to read (second axis) and; obstacles to activating the role of the professor in training young people to read in universities in a way that develops scientific research and serves the country's research priorities (third axis).

4.2 The role of university teaching objectives in promoting free and critical reading among young people in its academic and training educational programs (first axis)

Majority (88%) of the participants recognized the importance of having a generation who recognized reading as an important skill, while 4 percent disagreed with this notion.

80 percent of participants wanted the authorities in Saudi to promulgate the idea of the rights of reading while 5 percent of participants disagreed with the idea of the rights of reading. Of the 80 percent, 32 percent strongly believed that the country's stance on reading should be promulgated.

88 percent of participants agreed that people should generally know that women face challenges regarding reading. This finding holds significance considering that 95 percent of women responded to the questionnaire. However, 6 percent still believe that these challenges should not be talked about.

There was a consensus of 86 percent on finding negativity and finding solutions for it. 86 percent of participants also believed that students should be given the ability and skill through reading to solve problems.

77 percent of participants believed that women should be given significant roles at all levels to promote reading while 13 percent disagree that such roles are not required. This finding was significant given that most participants were University degree holders who were working.

4.3 Important Procedures and Teaching Mechanisms that must be Implemented by Those Responsible for Teaching.

The second axis explores these mechanisms in relation to reading. The table below summarizes the data from the research.

Table 1: Important Procedures and Teaching Mechanisms necessary for Implementation

Questions/ Focus		
Adding a subject to all academic programs at the university that teaches free reading in the library, or on social media.	Strongly Agree	35%
	Agree	51%
	Neutral	10%
	Do not Agree	2%
	Strongly Disagree	2%
Inclusion of an elective course for all academic programs at the university on critical reading, speaking, and public speaking.	Strongly Agree	25%
	Agree	68%
	Neutral	6%
	Do not Agree	1%
	Strongly Disagree	0%
Training young people to practice reading inside the university, and informing them of their rights and societal duties through comprehensive reading about them.	Strongly Agree	28%
	Agree	67%
	Neutral	3%
	Do not Agree	0%
	Strongly Disagree	2%
Holding specialized training courses and workshops for faculty members to provide them with the knowledge and skills necessary to develop their abilities to teach students reading subject matter, each according to his specialization.	Strongly Agree	38%
	Agree	57%
	Neutral	3%
	Do not Agree	0%
	Strongly Disagree	2%

86% of the respondents were in agreement (51% agree; 35% strongly agree) that adding a subject to all academic programs at the university that teaches free reading in the library, or on social media is essential in developing critical reading skill among students; whereas 2% strongly disagree with this and the remaining 3% of the respondents were indecisive.

93% of the respondents were in agreement (68% agree; 25% strongly agree) that the inclusion of an elective course for all academic programs at the university on critical reading, speaking, and public speaking is essential in developing critical reading skill among students; 1% of the respondents disagreed while the remaining 6% were neutral in this matter.

Also from the table, it is obvious that training young people (students) to practice reading inside the university, and informing them of their rights and societal duties through comprehensive reading about them would enhance their critical reading skill. This is so, as a great number (95%) of respondents were in agreement (67% agree; 28% strongly agree) with it; while 1% of the respondents do not agree with this statement. However the remaining 6% of the respondents were neutral on this.

Most (95%) of the respondents were in agreement (57% agree; 38% strongly agree) that *holding specialized training courses and workshops for faculty members to provide them with the knowledge and skills necessary to develop their abilities to teach students reading subject matter, each according to his specialization* is necessary in developing critical reading skill among students. However, 2% of them strongly disagreed while the remaining 3% were indecisive.

Conclusion

In conclusion, adding a subject to all academic programs at the university that teaches free reading in the library, or on social media is essential in developing critical reading skill among students. It was also revealed that the inclusion of an elective course for all academic programs at the university on critical reading, speaking, and public speaking is essential in developing critical reading skill among students. It is obvious that training young people (students) to practice reading inside the university, and informing them of their rights and societal duties through comprehensive reading about them would enhance their critical reading skill. Finally, holding

specialized training courses and workshops for faculty members to provide students with the knowledge and skills necessary to develop their abilities; to teach students reading subject matter to students, each according to his specialization is necessary in developing critical reading skill among them, not only in Arabic but also in the English language.

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